

The Role of Electronic Banking Services in Indian Banking Sector

Dr.S.Chandrasekaran

*Assistant Professor PG and Research Department of Commerce
Vivekananda College, Tiruvedakam West*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Chandrasekaran, S
& Mohan, M. "The
Role of Electronic
Banking Services in
Indian Banking Sector."
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 95–98.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2552222](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552222)

Mr.M.Mohan

*Ph.D. Scholar PG and Research Department of Commerce
Vivekananda College, Tiruvedakam West*

Abstract

The banking sector in India has realized a some changes. And to meet the challenges of changing needs and perceptions of customers, new regulations over the years and countless advances in technologies, most of the banks have introduced to take an innovative approach towards banking with the objective of generating more value for customers in the banks. Today we have electronic payment system laterally with currency notes. India's financial sector is moving towards a scenario, where it can have new instruments along with liquidity and safety. The arrival of the card, an introduction of Electronic Clearing Service (ECS) in late 1990's, , the introduction of Electronic Funds Transfer, Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), an introduction of NEFT (National Electronic Funds Transfer), mobile banking, online banking are the various innovations in banking. Banks are investing heavily in the adoption of these innovations. This paper highpoints the benefits of changing banking trends.

Keywords: Electronic banking, Benefits, Impact and Importance, Services, India.

Introduction

Banking in India has been over a long journey. Indian Banking Sector has perceived a some changes. The usage of e-banking by the enterprises came into existence in mid-90's. e banking came into existence in better numbers because of low operating costs. First, it is in the form of ATM's and phone transactions. Recently it misshapen to the internet a new channel between customers and banks which benefits both. The main aim of e-banking services is to provide the customers a much faster services with low cost. From the last twenty years, the banking sector has selected a new method of banking based on the progress of information technology. In addition to these customers, transaction and communication abilities are fastened based on information technology. Now all the banks have started with the concept of E-banking services, like ATMs, credit cards, debit cards, telephone/mobile banking, internet banking, call centers, etc. The role of banking is redefined from a mere financial intermediary to service provider of various financial services under one gableacting as a financial supermarket. Penetrating competition among the banks has redefined the concept of the entire banking

system. The banks are looking for new ways not only to attract but also to retain the customers and gain the competitive advantage over their competitors.

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the need of E-banking services in India.
2. To know the impact of E-banking services in India.
3. To aware the importance pertaining to E-banking services in India.
4. To realize the benefits of E-banking services in India.

Methodology

Secondary data has been collected for this paper. The same has been gathered from various sources like journals, books, magazines, and reports.

Review of Literature

VijayaRatnam and SugunaKumari (2005) in their article “Customer Service in Commercial Banks in the New Era” concludes that to ensure their competitive edge in future, they have to fight with opponents regarding quality of their service. The challenges that lie before the bankers are four fold. First, they essential to satisfy customer needs that are complex and difficult to manage. Second, they need to face up to increased competition from within the sector and from new participants coming into the financial sector market. Third, they need to address the stresses based in the supply chain. Finally, they must continually create new products and services to attract and retain the customer.

Venkatesh and Periasamy (2006) in their article “Role of e-Banking in Emerging Scenario” have stated that the prospects, therefore, lie in firming the package of innovative banking services already provided as well as offering complementary services where the banking and foreign exchange financial service industries should start to concentrate towards the customer-oriented outlook with positive regulations to face the 22nd century customers.

Tammy Parker and Michael Parker (2012) in their study investigate electronic banking in Finland and its historical development. Data are collected for MI and GDP to calculate money velocity. Money velocity is found to substantially decrease in 1991 due to a redefinition of MI Finland, but more importantly, rapidity showed a slight downward trend before the redefinition and following the redefinitions. This downward trend goes against what we would have expected to occur in an environment of increasing technology in the banking sector.

What is E-banking?

Electronic funds transfer means computer systems are used to achieve financial transactions electronically. The EFT is used for electronic payments and customer initiated dealings where the cardholder pays using credit or debit card.

The transaction types are, Withdrawal, deposit, inter-account transfer, inquiry, administrative transactions that covers non-financial transactions including PIN change. Electronic Fund Transfer transactions need authorization, and a means to match the card and card holder. EFT transactions require the cardholder’s PIN to send online in encrypted form for validation by the issuer of the card. Electronic funds transfer transactions are initiated during e-banking procedures. The different methods of e-banking are

- Online banking
- Short message service banking
- Telephone banking
- Mobile banking
- Interactive -TV banking

Importance of E-Banking

E-banking provides many advantages for banks and customer's .e-banking has made life much calmer and banking much faster for both customers and banks.

Main advantages are as follows.

- It saves time spent in banks
- It provides ways for international banking.
- It provides banking throughout the year 24/7 days from any place have internet access.
- It provides well-organized cash management for internet optimization
- It delivers convenience regarding capital, labor, time all the resources needed to make a transaction.
- Taking advantage of integrated banking services, banks may compete in new markets, can get new customers and grow their market share.
- It provides some security and privacy to customers, by using state-of-the-art encryption and security technologies.

Impact of E-Banking Services in India

Technology has been one of the most significant issues for the development of the nation. Information and communications are a significant part in the field of technology which is used for accessing, processing, storage and broadcasting of information electronically. E-banking is one of the emerging trends in the banking and is singing a unique role in strengthening the banking sector and cultivating service quality. It has enabled the banks to handle the payments electronically and inter-bank settlement faster and in large volumes. Customers can view the accounts, get account statements, transfer funds, purchase drafts by just making a few key punches. Availability of ATMs and plastic cards, EFT, electronic clearing services, internet banking, mobile banking, and phone banking to a large extent avoid customers going to branch premises and has provided a broader range of services to the customers.

Benefits of E-Banking

- Account Information: Real-time balance information and summary of day's transaction.
- Fund Transfer: Manage your Supply-Chain network, effectively by using our online hand transfer mechanism. We can effect fund transfer on a real time basis across the bank locations.
- Request: Make a banking request online.
- Downloading of account statements as an excel file or text file.
- Customers can also submit the following requests online: Registration for account statements by e-mail daily/weekly/fortnightly/monthly basis.
 - Stop payment or cheques
 - Cheque book replenishment
 - Demand Draft/Pay-order
 - An Opening of fixed deposit account
 - An Opening of Letter of credit
- Customers can integrate the System with his own ERP
- Bill Payment through Electronic Banking
- The Electronic Shopping Mall
- Effecting Personal Investments through Electronic Banking
- Investing in Mutual funds
- Initial Public Offers Online

Limitation of E-Banking

- Safety situations around ATMs.
- Misuse of bank cards by fraudsters at ATMs.
- The Danger of giving your card number when buying on-line.

E-Banking Services in India

In India, since 1997, when the ICICI Bank first offered internet banking services, today, most new-generation banks proposal the same to their customers. All major banks provide e-banking services to their customers. The following vital E-banking services are provided the Indian banking sector.

- Popular services under e-banking in India
- ATMs (Automated Teller Machines)
- Telephone Banking
- Electronic Clearing Cards
- Smart Cards
- EFT (Electronic Funds Transfer) System
- ECS (Electronic Clearing Services)
- Mobile Banking
- Internet Banking
- Telebanking
- Door-step Banking

Conclusion

With time, the thought of internet banking has got attention in the Indian context. Most of the banks have already executed the e-banking facilities, as these facilities are beneficial to both, i.e., banks as well as consumers. The banks are facing many challenges, and many opportunities are available with the banks. Many financial innovations like ATMs, Credit cards, RTGS, Debit cards, Mobile banking, etc. have completely changed the face of Indian banking. Thus, there is a model shift from the seller's market to buyer's market in the industry, and finally, it affected at the bankers level to change their approach from "conventional banking to convenience banking" and "mass banking to class banking." The shift has also increased the degree of accessibility of a mutual man to the bank for his variety of wants and requirements. In years to come, e-banking will not only be an acceptable mode of banking but will be favoured mode of banking.

References

- <https://www.ijcsn.com/Documents/Volumes/vol2issue3/ijcsn2012020303.pdf>
- <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/information-technology/importance-of-e-banking.php>
- Jiaqin Yang & KhTanveer Ahmed Recent trends and developments in e-banking in an underdeveloped nation-an empirical study *Int. J. Electronic Finance*, vol.3, no. 2, 2009.
- Kumar Nidhi, "E-Banking in India: Challenges and Opportunities" *Journal of ICRISMET*, vol.16, pp. 931-937.
- Tammy Parker & Michael Parker, "Electronic banking in Finland and the Effect on Money Velocity," *Journal of Money, Investment and Banking*, 2012.
- Venkatesh & Periasamy P, "Role of e-banking in Emerging Scenario," *Professional Banker*, vol.6, no.4, 2006, p.57.
- VijayaRatnam & SugunaKumari, "Customer Service in Commercial Banks in the New Era," *Professional Banker*, vol. 5, no. 11&12, 2005, p.47.